

Effect of Competence, Workload, Job Characteristics and Job Satisfaction to Employee Performances (Literature Review Research on Human Resource Management)

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Abstract- Employee performance determines the sustainability of an organization. However, there are many factors that influence the employee performance in an organization. This review will present how the competency, workload, job satisfaction and job characteristics influence the employee performance. The results showed that competency, job characteristics and job satisfaction have positive correlation with the employee performance. On the other hand, the job workload can be positive and negative effect to the employee performance. This result is useful as a consideration in determining an organization's policies to map of human resources and employee performance targets in an organization so that optimal performance is obtained to support the sustainability of the organization.

Keywords - competency, workload, job characteristics, job satisfaction, employee performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

An organization needs the competitiveness of Human Resources (HR), so that the existence of Human Resources is increasingly important and has a very strategic role. An organization is successful if in every process of implementing activities always prioritizes human resource aspects. The employee performance indicators are important for optimization of human resources in the organization. Human resources must have a role, function and be able to compete within the organization. HR competency is an important prerequisite because quality competency will demonstrate capabilities as expected. Future organizational demands include that organizations must have competitive advantages in terms of product quality, service, costs, and professional human resources.

The performance of an organization's employees is influenced by job characteristics (Mauladi et al., 2019), job workload (Setyowati & Nurhayati, 2020), competency (Idayanti et al., 2020) and job satisfaction. Identifying factors that influence employee performance is an important thing that can be used by an organization to make the human resources mapping within the organization. So that, the employee has the function and play an optimal role and the employee performance can also be optimal. The relationship between these factors related to employee performance is needed to provide an overview of human resource management in an organization to improve employee performance based on competency factors, workload, job characteristics and employee job satisfaction in accordance with the human resource profile they have.

Human resources can be used as assets whose efficiency and productivity must be increased, so that organizations can create conditions for employees to be able to develop themselves and improve their abilities and skills optimally. The capacity of each employee will be different. There is a need for employee competency mapping, so that they can carry out work in accordance with the organization's expectations. According to Purwanto & Soliha (2017), job characteristics are an effort to identify the tasks of a job, so that an organization must identify the human resources they have in accordance with their capacity/ competence. The difference between the employee capability shows the level of task difficulty which reflects the workload, namely the tasks that must be completed by employees according to the employee's abilities (Harini et al 2018). Job characteristics, apart from being able to create employee job satisfaction, will also influence employee work results and employee commitment to the organization (Priyono & Marnis, 2008). Organizations that experience changes in an increasingly competitive business environment will give rise to employee dissatisfaction, which can disrupt or hinder the stability and success of the organization. However, employees who are satisfied at work will develop motivation within themselves to act to achieve higher work performance and employee performance will also increase, so it is important to identify and analysis the correlation of factors that can influence employee performance to support organizational performance. This article will present the relationship between several factors that influence employee performance, including job characteristics, workload, job satisfaction and human resource competence.

II. THEORITICAL REVIEW

Competence

Competence is an ability based on skills and knowledge which is supported by work attitudes and their application in carrying out tasks and work that refers to the specified work requirements (Sutrisno, 2016). Etymologically, competency is defined as a behavioral dimension of expertise or excellence in a leader or staff having good skills, knowledge, and behavior. According to Spencer and Spencer (1993), competence is an underlying characteristic of an individual that is linked to the results obtained in a job.

The basic characteristics of competence mean that ability is something that is chronic and in part a person's personality and predictable behavior in a work assignment. Spencer and Spencer (1993), competence is a characteristic that underlies a person and is related to the effectiveness of an individual's performance in their work. Based on this definition, competence is a deep and inherent part of a person's personality and behavior that can be predicted in various situations and work tasks.

Workload

Workload refers to all activities involving employees, the time required to carry out tasks and work both directly and indirectly (Johari et al., 2018). Workload is a comparison of the total standard time to complete tasks and work to the total standard time (Kasmir, 2019). The definition of workload can be concluded from the definitions above, namely the perception of workers regarding the activities that must be completed within a certain time as well as efforts to deal with problems at work. Workload can be measured by the total time required to complete a particular task so that a worker is able to complete and adapt to a number of tasks given, so this does not become a workload. However, if the worker is unsuccessful then these tasks and activities become a workload. Hastutiningsih (2019) classifies workload into 3 (three) levels as follows.

a. Workload above normal

The time used to complete the work is greater than the available work hours or the volume of work exceeds the work capacity.

b. Normal workload

The time used to complete work is equal to the available working hours or the volume of work is equal to the worker's capabilities.

c. Workload below normal

The time used to complete the work is less than the available working hours or the volume of work is lower than the work capacity.

Meanwhile, Tarwaka (Tjibrata et al., 2017) stated the workload indicators as follows:

a. Time load shows the amount of time available in planning, implementing, monitoring tasks or work.

b. Mental effort load means the amount of mental effort in carrying out a job.

c. Psychological stress load which shows the level of job risk, confusion and frustration

Job Characteristics

Job characteristics are an effort to identify the task characteristics of a job, how these characteristics are combined to form different jobs and their relationship with motivation, job satisfaction and employee performance (Purwanto & Soliha, 2017). Job characteristic indicators mean what characteristics of the job characteristics an employee show. The job characteristic indicators according to (Warapsari, 2019) are as follows:

- a. Diversity of skills (skill variety), the extent to which the job requires a variety of activities different so that the job can use a number of different skills and talents.
- b. Task identity (task identity), the extent to which the job requires the completion of all pieces of work in a complete and identifiable manner.
- c. The meaning of the task (task significance), the extent to which the work has a substantial impact on the lives or work of other people.
- d. Autonomy (autonomy), the extent to which the job provides the individual with considerable freedom, independence, and latitude in scheduling the job and in determining the procedures to be used in completing the job.
- e. Feedback from work (feedback from work), the extent to which the implementation of work activities required by the job results in the individual obtaining direct and clear information regarding the effectiveness of his or her performance.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that pleases and loves one's job. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline, and work performance (Hasibuan, 2017). Job satisfaction can also be expressed as an employee's emotional state where there is a meeting point between the value of compensation for work services by the company and the level of compensation desired by the employee. Job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response to various aspects or aspects of a person's work so that job satisfaction is not a single concept. A person can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of a job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects. Job satisfaction is the (positive) attitude of workers towards

their work, which arises based on an assessment of the work situation. This assessment can be carried out on one's work, the assessment is carried out as a sense of appreciation for achieving one of the important values in the work. Satisfied employees like their work situation more than they dislike it. Both financial and non-financial. Job satisfaction is not always a strong motivational factor for achievement, because employees who are satisfied at work do not necessarily increase their work performance. There are five factors that can influence job satisfaction (Kreitner and Kinicki, 2001) namely as follows:

- a. Fulfillment (Need fulfillment), satisfaction is determined by the level of job characteristics provide opportunities for individuals to fulfill their needs.
- b. Difference, satisfaction is a result of meeting expectations. Fulfillment of expectations reflects the difference between what is expected and what an individual obtains from his or her work. If expectations are greater than what is received, people will be dissatisfied. On the other hand, individuals will be satisfied if they receive benefits above expectations.
- c. Value achievement (Value attainment), satisfaction is the result of the perception that work provides fulfillment of important individual work values.
- d. Justice (Equity), satisfaction is a function of how fairly individuals are treated in the workplace.
- e. Genetic components job satisfaction is a function of personal traits and genetic factors. This means that differences in individual characteristics have an important meaning in explaining job satisfaction in addition to the characteristics of the work environment.

Performance

Performance comes from the words job performance or actual performance which means work performance or achievement what a person achieves (Mangkunegara, 2017:67). The definition of performance (work achievement) is the quality and quantity of work results achieved by an employee in carrying out his functions in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. According to Wijoyo (2021), performance is the result or overall level of success of a person during a certain period in carrying out tasks against predetermined work standards, targets or goals or criteria.

Performance appraisal is an assessment to improve an employee's performance. Performance appraisal generally covers both qualitative and quantitative aspects of work implementation (Handoko, 2001). Performance appraisal is one of the main elements of the workforce, which is sometimes also called performance review, employee assessment, performance evaluation, employee evaluation, or personnel ranking. All these terms relate to the same process.

Performance measurement is used to see and compare the output or results of the extent to which activities have been carried out well and have been achieved (Supriyanto & Maharani, 2013). There are differences in performance measurement methods. According to Supriyanto & Maharani (2013), performance benchmarks are classified into 3 (three), namely: 1) Quantity, namely the amount that must be completed 2) Quality, namely the quality produced 3) Timeliness, namely compliance with the predetermined time.

III. METHOD

The preparation of this scientific article was carried out using a qualitative approach and conducting a study literature or library research with a focus on analyzing factors that can influence employee performance. Employee performance plays an important role in the success of an organization in achieving goals in accordance with the established vision and mission. The data used in this research was obtained through reviewing literature that was relevant to the written theory and involved discussion. Apart from that, this research also conducted an analysis of scientific journals, both national and international.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the literature review state that there are many factors that influence employee performance. Based on the results of previous research reviews, it is stated that there are a number of factors that positively and negatively influence employee performance, namely competence, workload, job characteristics and job satisfaction. In detail the influence of these factors can be stated as follows:

The Influence of Competency on Employee Performance

Competence factor has a positive effect on employee performance at a hotel in Seminyak Kuta, Bali (Idayanti et al., 2020). The low competency in that research is caused by a lack of training activities provided and a lack of coordination between departments so that communication is less effective. Apart from that, there are also differences in the character of each employee in the company. Triwarni & Evanita (2021) also reported that competence has a positive effect on job satisfaction and work performance of village officials in Pariaman City. The population used in the research was village officials in Pariaman City and the research sample was 200 respondents. Data analysis using SEM AMOS. In other research Kaitana & Sendow (2021), stated that work competency, job satisfaction, and work environment together influence employee work performance at PT Bank Papua Sorong

Meanwhile, Pitoey et al (2021) analyzed the influence of workload, work competency, work environment and work motivation on employee performance, both simultaneously and partially. The research results showed that workload,

work competency, work environment and work motivation together had a positive and significant effect on performance variables. Partially, workload has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Work competency has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

Effect of Workload on Employee Performance

Workload has a significant positive effect on employee performance (Idayanti et al., 2020). This research showed that to improve employee performance, communication within the company must be well established so that all workloads faced can be overcome, such as through increasing employee competency which will have a positive impact on employee performance. In line with research by Neksen et al (2021), it is explained that workload and working hours have a significant positive effect on the performance of PT Grup Global Sumatra employees. The different result by Silaban et al. (2021), reported that workload has a negative effect on organizational commitment and employee performance. The results of other research that conducted in a limited population by means of census or saturated sampling stated that workload had a significant effect on work stress, workload had a significant effect on employee performance, and work stress had a significant effect on employee performance at the Sikka Regency Land Office (Paulus & Wellem (2022). Emalia (2022) reported about the determination of job satisfaction and performance, in these results showed that there is an influence between 1) workload on job satisfaction; 2) compensation for job satisfaction; 3) workload on employee performance; 4) compensation for employee performance; and 5) job satisfaction with employee performance. According to Sudarsih & Supriyadi (2019), conducting an analysis examines how to improve the performance of outsourced employees through workload and work discipline by using job satisfaction as an intervening variable, showed a significant direct negative influence of workload on employee job satisfaction and performance, a significant direct positive influence of work discipline on employee job satisfaction and performance, and job satisfaction a significant direct positive influence on employee performance. The research results also found a significant indirect effect of workload and discipline on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable, but the magnitude was weaker than the direct effect.

The Influence of Job Characteristics on Employee Performance

The results of research by Bagia et al. (2020), stated that work characteristics have a significant influence on employee performance in district governments in Bali Province. In this research testing the influence of (1) work involvement, job characteristics and organizational commitment, (2) work involvement, (3) job characteristics and (4) organizational commitment on the performance of sub-district employees in government in Bali Province. The same thing was conveyed by Sabra (2020), that there is a significant influence of job characteristics and all its dimensions, namely job autonomy, skill diversity, task identity, task significance, and feedback on job performance.

Another research conducted by Mauladi et al. (2019) related to the influence of job characteristics, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence on job satisfaction and performance of nurses at Gresik Islam Hospital, showed that job characteristics influence performance, emotional intelligence also influences job satisfaction and performance, while spiritual intelligence only influences job satisfaction, and the influence of job characteristics on job satisfaction and intelligence spiritual influence on performance is not significant. Finally, job satisfaction also affects performance.

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Teacher satisfaction affects teacher performance and also student performance (Maldrine & Henry, 2020). Other research states that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance (Agustin, Tobing, & Komariyah, 2021). There is an influence of competence and soft skills on employee performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable (Ramadhan et al., 2021). Competency and soft skills have a direct positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, then competency, soft skills and job satisfaction also have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Indirectly, job satisfaction can positively influence employee performance and soft skills through satisfaction. Meanwhile, Anwar (2021) stated that job satisfaction and workload among workers still have many problems affecting the workforce, especially in the human resources aspect. Anshori et al. (2023), reported that job satisfaction has a significant impact on performance of employee. In this research showed that the satisfaction derived from one's job is a crucial factor influencing a teacher's overall performance. If a teacher possesses exemplary competence, the absence of a sense of contentment and alignment with their work may hinder the creation of optimal outcomes. Furthermore, excessive, and untimely work demands that surpass their capacity can impede performance, as a heightened workload diminishes satisfaction in their tasks. Teachers experiencing satisfaction in their duties are likely to see improvements in their overall performance. Hakim et al. (2019), stated that there was correlation between job satisfaction and employee performance is evident in the organizational context, as companies with more satisfied employees tend to demonstrate higher effectiveness compared to those with less satisfied employees. The impact of job satisfaction on performance is substantial. Job satisfaction plays a role in influencing employee performance. When employees experience satisfaction in their work, they are more likely to complete tasks punctually, thereby positively impacting their overall performance. (Setyowati et al, 2021)

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for competency factors, workload, job characteristics and job satisfaction on employee performance

Based on theoretical studies, relevant literature research, and descriptions in the conceptual framework above, it can be concluded that the variables of competency, workload, job characteristics and job satisfaction have an influence on employee performance. Apart from these four variables, there are also a number of other variables that also influence employee performance, namely:

1. Communication (Idayanti et al., 2020)
2. Work environment (Pitoy et al., 2021; Kaitana & Sendow, 2021)
3. Emotional intelligence (Mauladi et al., 2019)
4. Work discipline (Sudarsih & Supriyadi, 2019)

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the literature analysis (review), there are several factors that influence employee performance, namely competence, workload, job characteristics and job satisfaction. All literature states that competency, job characteristics and job satisfaction have a positive effect on employee performance. There are differences in research results related to workload factors on employee performance, results stated that workload has a negative effect on employee performance, and some argue that workload has a positive effect on employee performance. Managing these factors is very important to improve employee performance, organizational performance, and the sustainability of an organization.

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